

Synthesis and applications of polyaniline/zeolitic imidazolate framework composites: Implications on the electrochemical performance and perspective for enhanced functionality- Review

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Abstract: Polyaniline (PANI) has recently gained attention due to its cost-effectiveness, environmental stability, multiple oxidation and reduction reactions, ease of handling, and electrochemical performance. Conversely, zeolitic imidazolate frameworks have attracted interest because of their exceptional morphology, high surface area, tunable porosity, suitable functional linkers, and metal sites. This chapter explores recent advances in the synthesis of PANI doped with ZIF composites and their potential applications in batteries, conversion technologies, electrocatalysis, supercapacitors, and electrochemical sensing. Additionally, insights into the Tafel constant in HER analysis are discussed, along with its practical benefits. By reviewing current research developments, we aim to elucidate strategies to optimise the electrochemical performance of polyaniline doped with zeolitic imidazolate frameworks, known as PANI/ZIF composite.

Keywords: PANI, ZIF, Electrochemical applications, Electrochemical performance.

1. Introduction

The search for more effective energy conversion, storage, and electrochemical sensing materials has intensified globally. This search is driven by the need to find more sustainable energy systems used in portable devices (Das et al., 2022; Lai et al., 2024). Conducting polymers such as polyaniline (PANI) have attracted researchers' attention due to their cost-effectiveness, electrical conductivity, and their outstanding environmental stability (Muharemovic et al., 2009; Mashao et al., 2019). The outstanding properties of PANI arise from its backbone

structure, consisting of alternative ring heteroatoms (Molapo et al., 2012). Moreover, PANI exists in different forms, depending on the number of atoms and protons in its structure. Among these forms, the emeraldine form exhibits outstanding conductivity. The outstanding conductivity of the emeraldine form of PANI arises from its partially oxidised structure (Ahlatcioglu et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2024).

Meanwhile, Metal Organic Frameworks such as Zeolitic Imidazolate Frameworks (ZIFs) have been considered due to their adaptable chemical properties and porosity. Furthermore,

researchers have widely studied them due to their higher surface area and thermal stability (Mashao et al., 2019). ZIFs are made up of metal centers or ions coordinated to imidazole organic linkers (Monama et al., 2019). The three-dimensional structure of ZIFs comprises well-defined pores and channels, easily tailored for various applications. ZIFs have wide applications in catalysis, separation, and sensing (Malka et al., 2021). The advantages of ZIFs include their biodegradable nature, which can be discarded without causing harm to the environment (Arbab et al., 2024; Maleki et al., 2020).

Previous reports have shown that the integration of PANI with ZIF creates a composite that synergistically leverages the strengths of both materials. The composite is ideal for batteries, sensors, and supercapacitors (Tang et al., 2022). Several reports explored the electrochemical performances of conducting polymers and ZIFs. They further studied how to enhance their properties.

Avci et al. (2018) synthesised a novel multi-layered ZIF composite and highlighted that adding functional inorganic nanoparticles could enhance the catalytic activity while maintaining the structural properties of ZIF. Pašti et al. (2018) explored nanocarbons derived from polypyrrole and PANI, illustrating their exceptional electrochemical performance across different energy storage applications (Pašti et al., n.d.). Cao et al. (2023) examined the impact of ZIF-L morphology on the composite

membrane for heavy metal ion separation. Their findings highlighted that structural characteristics affect the electrochemical performance of composite materials (Cao et al., 2023).

Research by Tomczykowa and Plonska-Brzezinska (2019) offered a comprehensive overview of conducting polymers, outlining their biocompatibility and physicochemical properties essential to improve electrochemical performance (Tomczykowa & Plonska-Brzezinska, 2019). These studies collectively highlight the need for further research in designing PANI/ZIF composites to exploit their potential in various electrochemical applications. Despite the growing interest in PANI/ZIF composites for electrochemical applications, there is a lack of a comprehensive review that critically analyses how their synthesis methods and structural integration influence their electrochemical performance. Moreover, there is a lack of information in the literature that explains how these composites can be used for multifunctional applications. At present, PANI/ZIF-based electrochemical devices are in the early stages of commercialisation, still mostly at the prototype level (Muhammed et al., 2025). For instance, sensors using ZIF-7/PANI can detect cadmium and lead ions at sub-nanomolar levels (Guesmi et al., 2025), while ZIF-8/CNF/PANI composites show micromolar sensitivity for nitrite ions (Patri et al., 2024). To progress to real-world applications, researchers must

develop affordable, eco-friendly synthesis methods, such as room-temperature redox polymerisation or solvent-free vapour deposition (Vinodh et al., 2022). These methods should produce composites with well-controlled shapes, excellent conductivity, and long-term stability (Mashao et al., 2019; Vinodh et al., 2022).

Additionally, controlling particle size, pore structure, and the bond between PANI and the ZIF template is crucial to optimising the Tafel slope and exchange current density during hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) tests (Muhammed et al., 2025; Mashao et al., 2019). New strategies, like using ZIF precursors with multiple metals or ligands or doping PANI with functional linkers during synthesis, could enhance active sites and lower overpotentials (Muhammed et al., 2025; Mashao et al., 2019; Ramohlola et al., 2024).

Lastly, this review examines the latest findings on PANI/ZIF electrode materials for electrochemical applications. We summarise various synthesis methods, design principles, and how a material's structure relates to performance, focusing on enhancing Tafel parameters for HER. The aim is to offer clear guidance on designing the next generation of PANI/ZIF composites with high activity, stability, and durability. There are currently only a few metal-organic framework (MOF) templates used to prepare PANI/ZIF composites, such as ZIF-8, ZIF-67, and, more recently, ZIF-7 (Guesmi et al., 2025;

Muhammed et al., 2025; Patri et al., 2024; Vinodh et al., 2022). These hybrids combine large surface areas, adjustable pore sizes, and improved electron transport, which make them attractive for sensing and catalytic applications (Guesmi et al., 2025; Mashao et al., 2019; Patri et al., 2024; Vinodh et al., 2022). However, scaling up their synthesis from milligram-scale batches to gram-scale continuous processes while preserving uniform polyaniline coatings and the structural integrity of the MOF under electrochemical conditions remains challenging (Ma et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2025).

Precise control over particle size, pore architecture, and the interface between PANI and the ZIF framework is also critical for tuning key electrochemical parameters, like the Tafel slope and exchange current density in hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) tests (Muhammed et al., 2025; Mashao et al., 2019). Promising routes include using dual-metal or dual-ligand ZIF precursors and introducing functional linkers into PANI during synthesis (Guesmi et al., 2025; Muhammed et al., 2025; Patri et al., 2024). These strategies can increase active-site density and lower the overpotential required for hydrogen generation (Muhammed et al., 2025).

Therefore, this review examines the latest developments in PANI/ZIF electrode materials for electrochemical use. We summarise synthesis techniques, design principles, and the links between structural features and performance, with special attention to optimising Tafel parameters for HER. We aim

to offer clear guidance for the rational design of next-generation, environmentally friendly PANI/ZIF composites that achieve high activity, stability, and durability.

2. Structural Characteristics of PANI/ZIF Composites

2.1. Synthesis Methods

Synthesis of PANI/ZIF composites can be achieved through various methods. Each synthesis method influences the resulting materials' structural properties and electrochemical performance. The main synthesis techniques include:

2.1.1. In-Situ Polymerisation

In-situ polymerisation involves composite formation through the polymerisation of monomers. This results in the simultaneous formation of the composite structure and the polymer (Wei et al., 2009; Shahid et al., 2024; Agwuncha et al., 2024). In-situ polymerisation process uses dopants, monomers, and oxidants to form the required composite (Munaji et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2020). Furthermore, it uses ZIF precursors such as zinc nitrate and imidazole. These precursors are normally dissolved in a solvent, followed by the addition of aniline monomer and an oxidising agent such as ammonium persulfate. The reaction is conducted under controlled conditions, such as temperature and pH, to promote the polymerisation of aniline (Wei et al., 2009; Yang et al., 2023). Moreover, this method allows uniform distribution of PANI within the ZIF structure, which enhances the interaction

between the two components and improves conductivity (Kim et al., 2025).

The drawbacks of the in-situ polymerisation method include uncontrollable crystalline structure and morphology during the polymerisation stage. Moreover, the choice of solvent can significantly impact the properties of the final composite, which may require optimisation. Moreover, in situ polymerisation requires long reaction times and strict conditions. These factors may be unfavourable for large-scale applications (Zhao et al., 2020). Additionally, in situ polymerisation requires careful control over environmental cleanliness (Li et al., 2023).

2.1.2. Co-Precipitation

Co-precipitation is an effective technique used to synthesise PANI/ZIF composites. This method involves simultaneous precipitation of both PANI and ZIF from solutions (Castillo-Rodríguez et al., 2023; Bayat et al., 2024). The process typically starts with preparing a ZIF solution, followed by adding aniline and an oxidising agent (Bayat et al., 2024). Conditions such as pH and temperature are adjusted to facilitate the co-precipitation of PANI along with ZIF crystals. Co-precipitation can lead to well-defined composite structures and enhanced surface area, making it easier to scale up for industrial applications. Co-precipitation uses cost-effective equipment and materials to produce well-defined composite structures with controlled sizes and shapes (Ramandi & Entezari, 2023; Zhao et al., 2013). However,

achieving uniformity in the distribution of PANI and ZIF is difficult, which may lead to inconsistent electrochemical performance (Shah et al., 2018). Furthermore, careful control of temperature and pH is required to avoid incomplete reactions and the formation of undesired by-products (Shah et al., 2018).

2.1.3. Electrochemical Polymerisation

Electrochemical polymerisation, or electropolymerisation, involves the deposition of polymeric material onto the electrode material's surface (Maiti et al., 2012). This results in the formation of a cationic radical through the oxidation of the monomer. The electropolymerisation method is divided into anodic and cathodic groups (Coelho et al., 2016). The anodic method is used to prepare the most conductive compounds.

Polymer formation using electropolymerisation either involves radical ion

coupling or the reaction of a neutral monomer with a radical cation (Rodrigues et al., 2014). The polymer is formed by the reaction of radical cations with either neutral monomers or neighbouring radical cations. The electrochemical polymerisation of aniline results in a nonconducting PANI, leucoemeraldine state. The emeraldine form, the most conducting form of PANI, is formed in the reduced state. The cathodic electropolymerisation is rarely used to synthesise the conducting polymers because it produces an extremely low yield of conducting polymers (Xu et al., 2008; Simitzis et al., 2013). Poly (p-phenylenevinylenes) (PPVs), used in organic light-emitting devices, are the only conducting polymer produced through the cathodic polymerisation method (Schwarzer et al., 2008).

Figure 1. Instruments used for electrochemical polymerisation (Fomo et al., 2019)

Electropolymerisation has the benefit of combining synthetic and modification steps in one procedure (Coelho et al., 2016). During electrochemical polymerisation, the monomer undergoes electrochemical polymerisation, which forms free radicals adsorbed on the surface of the electrode. These radicals can subsequently undergo various reactions (Coelho et al., 2016). Moreover, electropolymerisation results in a polymer with physical characteristics inherent to semiconductors and metals while maintaining its conventional mechanical properties (Fomo et al., 2019).

2.1.4. Template-Assisted Methods

The template-assisted synthesis method uses a template material, such as silica spheres, to guide the formation of PANI composites. After polymerisation, the template is removed, resulting in composites with well-defined morphologies (Yu et al., 2010). This approach forms composites with specific shapes and sizes, and improves surface area (Zhang et al., 2004). However, template removal can be very complex, requiring additional steps affecting the yield (da Silva et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2018). Therefore, templates and additional processing steps can increase the overall cost compared to simpler methods (Pirzada & Altintas, 2021).

Table 1: Summary of the advantages and disadvantages of different synthesis methods

Synthesis Methods	Advantages:	Disadvantages	Ref
In-Situ Polymerisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allows uniform distribution of PANI within the ZIF structure Enhanced Conductivity Straightforward setup with fewer steps involved in the synthesis process. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficult to scale up Variations in thermal stability Poor mechanical properties 	(Rafiqi & Majid, 2017) (Cao et al., 2019) (Gao et al., 2021)
Co-Precipitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lead to well-defined composite structures Easy to scale up for industrial applications. Enhanced specific surface area of the composites. Produce well-defined composite structures with controlled sizes and shapes. Uses inexpensive materials and equipment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Homogeneity Issues Requires careful control of pH and temperature to avoid undesired by-products or incomplete reactions. Uses chemicals that might pose environmental concerns if not handled properly 	(Shukla et al., 2025) (Udayan et al., 2020) (Zhang et al., 2023)
Electrochemical Polymerisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allow precise control over the polymerisation process, including layer thickness and deposition rate. Improves the adhesion of PANI to ZIF surfaces, which can enhance durability and performance. It requires fewer toxic solvents and aligns with environmentally friendly practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex Setup Limited Scalability 	(Fomo et al., 2019) (Rodrigues et al., 2014)

<p>Template-Assisted Methods</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enables the creation of composites with specific shapes and sizes, which enhance surface area and performance. • Various templates can be used, allowing for customisation of the composite's properties. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The process of removing the template can be complex and may introduce additional steps, potentially affecting the yield. • The need for templates and additional processing steps can increase overall costs compared to simpler methods. 	<p>(Pirzada & Altintas, 2021)</p> <p>(Soni et al., 2018)</p>
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3. Electrochemical performance

Table 2: Comparison of PANI composites with varying structural properties, showing the main features and the specific capacitance of various PANI/ZIF composites. From these studies, the specific capacitance ranges from 79.8 F/g to about 20416.70 mF/g.

Type of composite	Main features	Specific Capacitance	Capacitance retention	Other Metrics	Ref
d-MOF-808/PANI	Improved transport charge and capacitance	188F/g at 30mV/s in 1M KOH	99.8% after 10,000 cycles	99.7% coulombic efficiency	(Ferhi et al., 2022)
PANI/UiO-66-NH ₂		79.8 F/g at 5 mV s ⁻¹	≥100% after 1000 cycles		(Milakin et al., 2023)
ZIF-67/PANI-NT/graphene		20416.70 mF/g at 0.05 Ma cm ⁻²	75% after 3000 cycles		(Ramandi & Entezari, 2022)
PANI/ZIF-67	High surface area and synergic effect	813.4F/g			(Boorboor Ajdari et al., 2018)
PANI/CoMn-LDH/ZIF-67	Enhanced stability and network structure	1048 F/g			(Yang et al., 2024)
Go@Co(OH) ₂ /PANI		15 times greater than ZIF-67 at 1A/g			(Xu et al., 2022)
Co-MOF/PANI	Enhanced electrochemical performance	504 F/g at 1A/g	90% after 5000 cycles		(Srinivasan et al., 2020)
Co ₃ O ₄ @PANI@NH ₂ -MIL-125				H ₂ evolution rate of about 1208μmolh ⁻¹ g ⁻¹ and apparent quantum yield of about 3%	(Sk et al., 2022)

4. Electrochemical Applications of PANI/ZIF Composites

PANI/ZIF composites have been found to have versatile applications in energy storage and conversion technologies (Guesmi et al., 2025; Muhammed et al., 2025; Patri et al., 2024). Their unique structural and electrochemical properties make them ideal candidates for use in energy storage devices such as supercapacitors and batteries, where their high surface area and excellent charge transport capabilities can deliver enhanced energy density and power output. Moreover, the tailorable composition and PANI/ZIF make-up enable their utilisation as highly efficient electrocatalysts for various energy conversion processes, including fuel cells and water splitting (Muhammed et al., 2025; Vinodh et al., 2022). Beyond energy applications, these materials have also shown promise in developing advanced sensors and biomedical devices, leveraging their sensitivity, biocompatibility, and ability to interface with biological systems (Muhammed et al., 2025).

4.1. Supercapacitors

Polyaniline bare electrode materials have been widely explored in supercapacitors. However, their electrochemical performance, mainly cycle stability, did not meet the criteria for commercial application (Vinodh et al., 2022). This poor cyclability in supercapacitors results in a shorter life cycle due to a rapid decline in its specific capacitance. Therefore, to

improve the supercapacitors' performance, scientists have attempted to form composites using a mixture of PANI with metal oxides, carbonaceous materials, MOFs, and metal hexacyanoferrates to form different PANI-based composites with various electrochemical properties (Vinodh et al., 2022).

PANI/ZIF composites have shown promise in supercapacitor applications due to their high surface area and tunable electrochemical properties. Their unique structure allows for efficient charge storage and rapid electron transfer, offering enhanced energy storage capabilities. For example, PANI/ZIF composites exhibit higher capacitance and better cycling stability as compared to bare PANI (Milakin et al., 2023; Ramandi & Entezari, 2023).

4.2. Electrocatalysis

Electrocatalysis is a field of science that involves the transfer of electrons through either oxidation or reduction to enhance the reaction rate (Łosiewicz & Popczyk, 2015). This is essential in energy conversion technologies such as fuel cells, water-splitting, and batteries (Łosiewicz & Popczyk, 2015; Ma & Sun, 2025). Over the past years, different researchers have explored PANI and ZIF composites as electrocatalysts. For instance, PANI and ZIF-67 composite were used to synthesise a multifunctional electrocatalyst with excellent electrocatalytic activities towards the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), oxygen evolution

reaction (OER), and oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in alkaline media. They have reported the improvement in the catalytic activity due to the synergetic cobalt nanoparticles, Co_3O_4 , and nitrogen-doped carbon combination from the

PANI/ZIF-67 composite (Khalid et al., 2018). Recent developments have shown that ZIF-derived materials, like iron-doped composites and Co_3O_4 nanoparticles, have superior oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) activity.

The voltammetric methods are widely used to compare and evaluate the HER activities of electrocatalysts (Murthy et al., 2017). In Tafel analysis, linear sweep voltammetry at lower scan rates is used. The current density (j) against potential (E) from the voltammogram is converted into the plot of $\log(j)$ against overpotential (η) (Murthy et al., 2018). The Tafel slope (b) is then extracted from the linear portion of the curve. Frequently, the exchange current density (j_0) is an additional parameter obtained from the Tafel plot through extrapolation (Ramohlola et al., 2024). The exchange current density and the Tafel slope are the important electrochemical parameters derived from the Tafel equation of an electrocatalyst. The Tafel equation is a widely used and well-verified expression, first experimentally established in the 1900s by Swiss chemist Julius Tafel (Fang et al., 2013; Murthy et al., 2018). The Tafel equation is widely applied to a wide range of reactions and processes, including corrosion, metabolism, and

photosynthesis (Murthy et al., 2018). The activity and the mechanistic aspects of HER are generally discussed based on the Tafel analysis in the literature (Pu et al., 2014). In this context, Tafel analysis in HER is invariably confined to obtaining b and j_0 from the experimental data. The current work provides physical insights into the Tafel constant (a) in the analysis of HER, and its advantages in practical applications.

Tafel Constant analyses for HER.

The dependency of current density j on the potential can be correlated to the electrocatalytic reaction rate v as follows:

$$j = nFv \quad (2.1)$$

where n represents the number of electrons F represents the Faraday constant.

j depends on the potential; therefore, v is dependent on potential.

It consists of several elementary steps, as follows:

Atom + ion or Heyrovsky step

Atom + atom or Tafel step

The above-mentioned elementary steps result in Volmer–Tafel and Volmer–Heyrovsky mechanisms. Heyrovsky, Volmer, and Tafel are the three rate-determining steps (RDS) possible for the above mechanisms. Regarding the two HER mechanisms described above, the catalytic current rises exponentially with increasing overpotential. However, the rate of this increase

varies for different RDSs. This presents an easier way to identify RDS and the likely mechanism that can occur at the catalyst surface (Pu et al., 2014; Fang et al., 2013).

A specific value of the Tafel slope is associated with one of the three RDSs described above and is not dependent on the catalytic current.

When the Volmer step becomes the RDS, a Tafel slope of 120 mV dec^{-1} is obtained. The Tafel or Heyrovsky step becomes the RDS when the slope is 30 or 40 mV dec^{-1} , respectively. The Tafel equation serves as an essential tool to determine the RDSs and the possible mechanism governing the performance of an electrocatalyst. The Tafel equation (Murthy et al., 2017) relating experimental potential dependency to the current density is as follows:

$$\eta = b \log(j) \quad (2.5)$$

The Tafel plot is generated by plotting the overpotential as a function of logarithmic current density (Mashao et al., 2019). In the equation above, η must be greater than RT/F ; otherwise, the current–potential relationship becomes linear or Ohmic.

Accordingly, the Tafel constant can be given by rearranging equation 2.5 when $\eta = 0$

4.3. Electrochemical Sensors

Polyaniline (PANI) and zeolitic imidazolate frameworks (ZIFs) are two materials that have unique properties that make them good candidates for use as electrochemical sensors. When cobalt-based ZIF (CoZIF) is added to PANI, it forms a composite material that has

better electrocatalytic properties, which makes it good for sensing hydrogen gas. Compared to pure PANI, this composite, PANI-CoZIF, shows better thermal stability and an enhancement in catalytic current and turnover frequency. This suggests that PANI-CoZIF could be useful in hydrogen fuel technology and gas sensing (Mashao et al., 2019). Similarly, combining PANI with ZIF-derived mesoporous carbon (ZIF-8-C) creates a hybrid material with a large interface surface area, which speeds up adsorption and charge transfer. The combined effect makes the response much stronger.

This synergy leads to a significant response enhancement in ammonia sensing, showcasing the potential for commercial applications in room-temperature gas sensors (Lu et al., 2024). Furthermore, the use of PANI with other MOFs, such as UiO-66-NH₂, has been shown to create effective electrochemical sensors for detecting heavy metal ions like cadmium, due to the chelation mechanism between metal cations and amine groups (Wang et al., 2017). The unique porosity and stability of ZIFs, including ZIF-8, make them ideal for encapsulating various guest species, enhancing their native physicochemical activity for electrochemical sensing applications (Paul et al., 2022). Overall, the combination of PANI with ZIFs leverages the high surface area, stability, and conductive properties of these materials, making them highly effective for a range of electrochemical sensing applications, including the detection of gases and small biomolecules (Feng et al., 2023).

4.4. Batteries and fuel cells

Polyaniline (PANI) and zeolitic imidazolate frameworks (ZIFs) have attracted much interest for use in batteries and fuel cells due to their special qualities and complementary effects when paired with other materials. PANI is frequently used in composite electrodes and electrocatalysts because of its high conductivity and environmental friendliness. By increasing active sites and improving stability, the electrochemical performance of fuel cells and

rechargeable batteries is improved (Li & Gong, 2020; Ali et al., 2023). ZIFs, especially ZIF-8, are known for their high surface areas and adjustable structures, which make them appropriate for energy storage devices like batteries and supercapacitors (Xu et al., 2017). Recent developments have shown that ZIF-derived materials, like iron-doped composites and Co_3O_4 nanoparticles, have superior oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) activity.

Figure 2. Synthesis, properties, and applications of polyaniline and its composites (Beygisangchin et al., 2024)

5. Challenges and Future Perspectives

Synthesis and application of polyaniline/zeolitic imidazolate frameworks present both advantages and challenges to

enhance electrochemical performance. The primary challenge is to achieve optimal conductivity, as effective electron transfer between PANI and ZIFs is crucial while maintaining structural integrity under

operational conditions (Xu et al., 2021). Moreover, the intricacies associated with the synthesis of hierarchical structures that maximise surface area and active sites can further complicate the fabrication process (Mangiri et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the prospects remain optimistic; these composites demonstrate marked enhancements in energy storage capabilities, with specific capacitance considerably exceeding those of their individual constituents (Xu et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2023). In addition, their prospective applications expand beyond energy storage to encompass catalysis and environmental remediation, capitalising on the distinctive properties of both PANI and ZIFs for multifunctional applications (Iravani et al., 2024) (Zhao et al., n.d.). As a result, addressing the synthesis challenges may yield innovative solutions across different applications.

6. Conclusion

Polyaniline /Zeolitic Imidazolate Framework composite presents a hybrid material that can be used in a variety of applications. Those applications include batteries, electrocatalysts, sensors, and supercapacitors. The key findings from this review suggest that incorporating ZIFs into PANI to form composites enhances the electrochemical stability and the structural stability of materials. However, the reaction mechanisms behind enhanced stability are not explicitly discussed in the literature. This review highlights the impact of synthesis methods on the electrochemical performance of PANI/ZIF

composites. There is insufficient information on the direct implications of the structural properties of PANI/ZIF on the electrochemical performance.

To fully exploit their potential, future research should focus on developing advanced characterisation techniques to quantify and identify the relationship precisely. Moreover, novel synthesis methods aimed at tailoring the structural properties of PANI/ZIF for large-scale production are required. Further research is also required to evaluate long-term stability and its possible practical application in real-world applications. This review has highlighted how different synthesis techniques critically influence the electrochemical behaviour and functionality of these composites. There is so much progress; however, challenges remain in achieving controlled morphology, structural stability, and enhanced charge transport mechanisms. Future research should emphasise the integration of advanced characterisation techniques, computational modelling, and scalable synthesis methods to guide the development of multifunctional and application-specific composites. With strategic innovation, PANI/ZIF composites can be tailored to meet the growing demands of energy, environmental, and sensing technologies sustainably and efficiently.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Gloria Mashao: Conceptualisation and writing original draft

Orpah Zinyemba: Supervising, writing, reviewing, and editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

Both authors declare that they have no known competing interests or personal relationships that could influence the work reported in this paper.

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